

Monitoring RTM Infiltration Behavior of TFP Preforms Using Near-Net-Shaped Transparent Cavities

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Agenda

- Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP)
- Challenges in mold design for RTM injections of TFP preforms
- Additive manufactured molds for RTM infiltration
- Accuracy of 3D-printed RTM molds
- Experimental results

Properties of different materials

Normalized dense specific elastic modulus of different lightweight material

Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP)

Process characteristics

- Near-net-shape production of variable-axial textile preforms
- Almost ideal utilization of anisotropic material properties
- Placement radii up to 5 mm

Complex infiltration behavior

Roving Base material Stitching yarn

Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP)

Process characteristics

- Preliminary studies about measurement of in-plane permeability
- Antisymmetric stitching pattern showed higher permeability
- CFD flow simulations of the experiments for predicting resin flow

Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP)

Overcoming the challenges by numerically predict resin flow

- Anisotropic material permeability needs to be evaluated by experiments
 - Race-tracking needs to be avoided
 - Experimental determination of out-of-plane permeability of TFP preforms is current subject of research
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- Additive manufactured tools enable rapid change of cavity geometries and inlet/outlet locations
 - Near-Net-Shaped cavities avoid race-tracking

(Transparent) molds for RTM injections

Comparison between different manufacturing technologies

- Complex TFP surfaces often require 3D-Milling
 - Surface Quality
 - Structural stiffness
 - Time consuming process
 - costly
- 3D-printing (Fused Deposition Modeling) technology
 - Cheap process
 - Comparatively fast
 - Not really transparent
 - Surface quality
 - Not sealed (porosity)
- 3D-printing (Stereolithography) technology
 - Transparent parts
 - Sealed structure
 - Brittle structures

(Transparent) molds for RTM injections

3D-printed approach

- 3D-Scan of fiber cutting tool
- Cross-section used as cavity cross section
- FDM print enables connection of various peripheral devices (pressure sensor etc.)

(Transparent) molds for RTM injections

3D-printed approach

- Top part SLA printed (transparent)
- Bottom part FDM printed (non-transparent)

(Transparent) molds for RTM injections

3D-printed approach – Evaluation of accuracy

- Zeiss GOM Metrology GmbH ATOS Q, MF 170
- Deviation to CAD model by best-fit

- SLA part after printing

- FDM part after printing

(Transparent) molds for RTM injections

3D-printed approach

Inlet

Outlet

Sealings

- Top and bottom part pressed together by quick release clamps

Injection experiment simple cavity

Thresholded video frame
with contour detection

Original video frame

Flow front height (px)
over time (frame)

- No race-tracking
- Flow front clearly visible through SLA printed cavity

Injection experiment complex cavity

- Race tracking at borders
- Inner sealings not sufficient
- Flow front clearly visible through SLA printed cavity

Thank you for your attention!

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